

SITE GS 80 SPHINX	DATE 3/1X/80	AREA CHAPEL	SQUARE	PAGE
MASONRY FILL to BEDROCK Feature No.	Coordinates: ABOVE "LEDGE BOX" (a2) to exposed bedrock S Forepaw		Levels	
			Top:	Bottom:
	SECTION OF MASONRY REMOVED — DIMENSIONS			
Diameter:	Width: N-S 33 cm.	Length: E-W 75 cm.	Depth:	

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
○	Between Blocks Rubbly sand-mortar, tan clay fragments	BUFF- TAN	CRUMBLY	CLAY & SAND Fine	T	Lm ✓ FRAGS:	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
	Other	BLUE FRIT PARTICLES, TAN CLAY CLUMPS MINUTE RED (PIGMENT?) PARTICLES					
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
	Other						
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
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						Al	
	Other						
○					T	Lm	Gp
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	Other						
○					T	Lm	Gp
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	Other						

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/	No./	B&W: Roll/	No./
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DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:50 PLAN E SECTOR	Feature Plan: 1:20 PLAN JAN. 1980	Sections:
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: Last week Abd al Laafi cleaned sand-debris fill w/ this feature staged in January 1980. Further brush cleaning was done 3/1X/80 and rectangular stone slabs 1 and 2 (as marked January) were taken out again. (Block 1 29x18x9 cm; 2: 33x13x11 cm; 3: 32x9x13 cm). Blocks are roughly squared and all show 1 side or more of straight face bearing fairly ~~and~~ regularly spaced shallow parallel straight line tool marks. A macro of these tool patterns photod. After more cleaning block 3 taken out mm. E of 1-2. Blocks marked sequentially on removal 1, 2, 3, 4 and by level i, ii, iii for this removal patch (levels higher than (i) in fill to W of section-removal area. Block 4. from level (i) taken from immediately against

face of bedrock paw, lengthwise E-W, E of Block 3 but on next highest level. As w/ Blocks 1, 2 in Jan. 1980, under Block 4 is dried fine compact tan clay mortar (crumbly) w/ red stains, loose sand. From this kind of fill between blocks removed come many tiny blue frit particles, larger flatish curved chunks of tan clay, fine-minute red (pigment?) particles. Q3 photo'd prior to removal of Block 4.

NOTE: Below Q3, Abd al Laafi clearing out E side of Q2 "Ledge Box"
Block 4 Dimensions: 46 x 11 x 13 cm. 1 face worked roughly straight, rest irregular

3/1X/80 Between 11:00 and 2:00 blocks 4i, 5ii, 5bii, 5cii, 5dii moved. Under all blocks characteristic tan clay frags (like bottom of dry wadi pool). In sandy matrix between blocks tiny frit - very blue - particles, particularly under 5bii. On a smooth (older) surface of 5ii at edge covered by 4i there is what looks to be red quarry mark perhaps of a sign 5. This edge broke off when removing 5ii and broke in 2 pieces through glyph. Will try to repair w/ epoxy. Blocks 6iii and 7iii (W side Q3) and blocks 8iii, 9iii fully revealed. Tops of these covered w/ dried out tan clay, limestone frags, some sloppy mortar banding, slightly reddish sand. Spaces between them do not look filled as blocks removed so far. Debris falls down into these spaces. And face of bedrock paw (now roughly vertical) looks as though it could cut in slightly below tops of 6, 7, 8, 9 iii. BUT FIRST A 2:00 PM LUNCH BREAK.

DIMENSIONS

BLOCK 5ii 46 x 27-18 x 9 5 faces worked flat (w. tool marks)
BLOCK 5bii 27 x 14 x 7 (end cut at angle, all sides rough hewn)
BLOCK 5cii 22 x 11 x 7.5 cm 2 faces worked straight
BLOCK 5dii 16 x 12 x 6 (rough hewn)

BLOCK 9iii has 90° cut to ground SE corner of large section slab.

4/1X/80 10:30 - 12:00 AM. STONES 6, 7, 8, 9 iii taken out. Underneath are large smooth (on one face) chunks of tan mortar. I wonder if their contours describe vessels they were kept in. These frags are smooth on one face, curled in various ways. A few more tiny specks of blue frit, but not so many as between higher levels of packing stones. Level IV packing blocks not so tightly packed - not as much fill between spaces. Bedrock very effloresced, curve under-inward turns out to be only an undulation-like recess. Limestone seems hard and consistent.

DIMENSIONS

BLOCK 6: 14 x 16 x 47-48 cm. (1 end, 2 sides roughly cut straight, rest rough hewn).
7: 10 x 18 x 42.5 cm (Both ends, one broad and one narrow face cut very straight (90° at ends). Bottom rough hewn in concave contour.)
8: 14 x 22 x 49 (One narrow, one broad face fairly flat, one end fairly flat at angle, rest rough hewn, angular cuts).
9: 12 x 16 x 34 (Generally squared, yet rough hewn).

7/1X/80 First thing in morning took up blocks 1-9 again. Then scrapped away fill under angle of large packing block on W side of Q3 down to top of parallel blocks 12-13. This fill was sandy, slightly reddish tinted w/ scattered blue frit specks, limestone frags, frags of fine tan clay. The ends of 12-13 found to butt against bottom of large angled packing block spanning levels i-iv on W. Next removed small block (fragmented) 11a.iv and then block 10.iv and 11.iv. Under these are a block similar to 10 in size and right under it and another small keyed-in block under 11. This actually about level w/ 12-13 so iv. level comprised of 2 layers of small packing blocks on E side Q3. The blocks under 10-11, which were quite loose and 12-13 seem more solid in place - perhaps mortared on bottoms.

10:30 - 12:00 AM Moved block 15v a kind of vertically placed key block (14v and 15v actually almost level w/ 12-13iv). Then moved 13iv and afterward 12iv with leverage of pick hammer. Following that 14 was lifted to expose level vi. [AT THIS POINT I SENT ABD AL LAAFI TO TAPISH w/ A NOTE ASKING ZAH, AS OUR INSPECTOR TO COME AND INSPECT OUR OPERATION. Zahi had gone to Abassiya headquarters and Mohammed Naqib took the note]. Under 12-14 there was a good deal of debris and many large fragments of the tan clay wedged between blocks. It appears as though this was used as a filler in packing masonry. There was almost no gypsum mortar except a small band on N edge of 14v. There were recovered many blue frit particles and small frags. Many again taken from sifting. Also fewer small red particles. The bedrock face gets very rough and heavily effloresced, the efflorescence adheres to the tan clay filler and this prys off to show on underside of frag. Crystalline structure like salt. Also, bedrock face shows some yellow clayish vein similar to bedrock exposed at abbed out inner side of N forepaw.

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			Top:	Bottom:
	DIMENSIONS			
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○					T	Lm	Gp
					D	Gr	Char
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Other							
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Other							
○					T	Lm	Gp
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DRAWN	Area Plan:	Feature Plan:	Sections:
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: DIMENSIONS

2:30-3:45 7/1x/80: Stones 17vi, 19vi, 20vii and 18vi taken out in that order. Tan clay filler gets more concentrated - thicker clumps. Photoford clay bedding under 17vi when lifted. Looks like possibly space filler between blocks getting to more a quartz or sand. Still getting some blue flint particles.

3:30-4:15 8/1x/80 Removed Stones 21, 22vii. These also bedded on matrix of tan moist clay - sand. Still getting blue and red particles. Also cut back W section at fill under angled block comprising upper part of section. Just behind few cms. of the red sand, tan clay cut there was another large irregular stone under the angled block. The underside of 21vii is crudely hacked concave as have been several of the other packing blocks. Perhaps to rest better on tan clay bedding.

22vi 10 x 14 x 41 cm. Roughly hewn.

10iv: 10 x 21 x 36 cm. Bottom face fairly even, rest rough cut.

11iv: 12 x 19 x 24 cm. Rough cut.

11aiv: 6.5 x 10 x 13 Rough cut

12.v: 10 x 23 x 50 irregular, Rough cut

13v: 17 x 18 x 51 Top straight cut w/ tool marks then reworked on S edge, rest rough cut, irregular for fitting

14.v: 10 x 26 x 35 Rough cut.

15v: 13 x 13 x 19 Bottom wedge shaped like 16v. A kind of Key stone

16v 10 x 12 x 18 Bottom wedged shape - a kind of Key stone Rough.

17vi 10 x 16 x 39. 5 sides very straight w parallel tool marks. 1 side and bottom cut rough, slightly concave.

18vi

19vi 18 x 21 x 49 Bottom face fairly even. Rest Rough cut w pronounced chisel marks.

20vi 11 x 18 x 31 Rounded top, crude concave bottom - 2nd half w. 21vi.

21vi 12 x 18 x 32. Rounded top. crude concave bottom. Rough.

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9/IX/80: Removed Blocks 24, 25, 27, 26 VIII in that order. Block 27 broke into many thin flakes on removal and will be replaced w. another outside slab. Under level VIII there was a thick layer of soil fill - again tan clay, yet sandier w/ buff crumbly gypsum mixed in. Still getting red and blue particles, the latter now sizeable to be called small fragments. The masonry of level IX seems more irregular w/ several odd small pieces. The face of the bedrock paw along the removal area here cutting in radically - just above surface of level IX, or much as 10 cm. It looks like packing stones and small frags inserted into - under roll of bedrock (inward). Just on the underside of the bedrock roll there is a band of moist concentrated tan clay.

DIMENSIONS

- 24 VIII 10 x 15.5 x 36 Top, 1 end, 1 side straight w/ parallel tool marks.
- 25 VIII 10 x 19 x 40 cm. Rough hewn, no tool marks
- 26 VIII 10 x 12 x 40 cm. Rough hewn, some tool marks show. E end cut at angle $\square$
- 27 VIII Fragmented on removal

10/IX/80 8:00-10:30. Moved packing blocks 31 IX, 32, 33, 36 IX, 29, 28 IX, 35 IX in that order. Underneath again a good deal of soil fill w/ many limestone chips. This was more a chalky buff gypsum at E side of the removal under, between 31 IX and 30 IX. 30 IX runs under E balk section and under the roll recess of bedrock face and likely cannot be moved. At W end, the fill is the more characteristic brown sand w/ tan clay. After removing 34, 29, and 35 the recessing inward of bedrock face cleared back 40 cm to find the vertical face again running downward (hence no opening into paw). Here the bedrock looks yellowish clay-like like that showing in inner side N fireplace. The fill in under the recess is darker brown, w/ grey mudspots. Moist tan clay adheres to top of recess (underside of roll) and on bedrock itself is effloresced layer that peels off. Still getting numerous small bits and particles of blue frit, red (pigment?). Also a few carbon flecks. As yesterday, a very few tiny bones - bird sized came up in sifting. The soil matrix has been cleared to a level of what appears to be irregular large limestone flakes. Under 34 IX and its general spot another large qebel-like cut stone ^(39 XI) abutting to 30 IX has been cleared. It also tucks under the roll in bedrock face and appears to rest on large limestone chip layer. As we are now down about 95 cm in the removal it appears we have reached the bottom of large set-in slabs (N side) and we have exposed the large blocks - chips on which the side slabs rest, and the former in turn rest on the bedrock ledge - all are seen in exposed elevation of side of paw inside feature Q2 - the ledge box.

In cleaning up the bottom for photography etc. became clear the large vertical inset slabs (N side) rest on large horizontally placed blocks, similar to those resting on ledge of inner side of N fireplace and we see these blocks in elevation of side of paw in back of Q2 ledge box. From soil fill in W section, under roll of bedrock 2 sherds extracted - 1 larger, both body sherds, non-diagnostic. Saved w/ soil adhering for possible thermoluminescence dating.

DIMENSIONS

- 28 IX Very crude thin slab soft limestone 6 x 16 x - broken in half on removal, one half disintegrated
- 29 IX Very crude slab thin soft yellow limestone 6 x 15 x 42 cm.
- 30 IX Remains in situ
- 31 IX 14 x 22 x 48 Very tough hewn
- 32 IX 5 x 10 x 30 Pressed on one side, one face, one end straight; faint roughly parallel tool marks
- 33 IX
- 34 IX 17 x 28 x 30 Rough hewn, hard limestone
- 35 IX 17 x 21 x 8 1 face, 2 sides, 1 end dressed straight. Roughly parallel tool marks on side and end.